
A Conceptual Study on Experiential Marketing: Marketing Strategy, Implementation Steps, Benefits, and Issues

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Introduction:

In today's competitive market, marketing specialists develop new strategies and tactics to ensure customer loyalty and customer retention, concepts that integrate a brand's ability to gain repeat purchases. The concept of experiential marketing has been globally embraced as a guide to designing memorable experiences that succeed in satisfying target consumers (Chang 2020). Customers' behavior designates differentiation in consuming diverse products and creates positive or negative experiences, the reason why businesses create several experiences for their consumers as a way to encourage interaction with the products, developing various positive reactions or perceptions (Ihtiyar et al. 2019).

Consumers have changed their needs, being more focused on experiences that are stimulating their sensations and emotions when they interact with a brand (Carù and Cova 2008). For this reason, the business-to-consumer (B2C) field was chosen to be approached in this study on the development of experiential marketing strategy. Accordingly, a new promotion strategy is required, one that enables consumers to experience marketing touchpoints around the landscape of consumption through personalized interaction design using new technology

(Rather 2020), especially in times when information and digital technologies advanced (Kuzior and Lobanova 2020).

The last few years have seen considerable growth in published scientific papers regarding the impact of experiential marketing strategy on consumers. Understanding customers' reactions to the involvement with a specific brand is one of the main objectives of marketing these days. Nevertheless, the complex field of experiential marketing implementation and evaluation strategies is not as well investigated as other paradigms in the vast field of marketing, as both theoretical and empirical research (Ihtiyar et al. 2019). Consequently, further research is needed based on the outcomes that experiential marketing touch points bring to both companies and consumers. The purpose of the study is to identify the opinion of the worldwide marketing experts concerning the experiential marketing strategy, underlying the keys to a successful event built around the needs, preferences, and values of consumers. Therefore, in this study we investigate the essential elements of an experiential marketing event that immerses consumers in memorable experiences, seeking to answer the research question: What are the main steps of implementing an experiential marketing strategy with a positive impact on both customers' value

and business outcomes? To answer this question, the following objectives have been established:

- O1. Develop a deeper understanding of experiential marketing, its implementation steps, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and benefits;
- O2. Explore the challenges of creating experiential marketing touchpoints;
- O3. Prospect the current dynamics and future look of experiential market

Literature of Review:

Experiential marketing is one marketing concept which has been used widely in different industries in recent years. Liu et al. (2016). Holbrook and Hirschman (1982) introduced experiential sight of consumption as an alternative to the information-processing perspective. According to these authors, Fantasies, Feelings, and Fun (3Fs) are the goals and criteria for successful consumption in the experiential view. In other words, in experiential consumption, the rational and goal-directed customer of the information-processing model turns to a pleasure-directed individual that continuously looks for amusement, enjoyment, and “sensory-emotive” stimulation. Experiential marketing essentially concerned with the six senses: smell, vision, taste, hearing, touch and balance. It has grown in importance because traditional marketing has largely ignored the notion of act experiences. Experiential marketing is not a fad. It is being implemented in practice, yet is not accounted for in the various philosophies (concepts) of marketing. Michelli, (2007) described the five principles for turning ordinary into extraordinary products. One of the principles he described to offer a unique experience to the customers. Further he explained that instead of selling a

product with its features it's better to sell their traditional offering if they wrap experience around them. He mentioned that generating a unique customer experience has been as the success key for brands such as Starbucks. Lee et al. (2011) defined experiential marketing as a memorable memory or experience that goes deeply into the customer's mind. According to Kotler (2003), there are two types of marketing: traditional marketing and modern marketing. Modern marketing has overtaken traditional marketing due to the emphasizing on the concepts of customer experience and experiential marketing. Wu, M. Y., & Tseng, L. H. (2015). Defined that experiential marketing perspective is very broad and help in gaining customer satisfaction and loyalty. Cuellar, et al (2015) have described the companies can take advantage of Experiential Marketing and increase their long term sales and profit.

Objectives of Study:

1. To study the benefits of Experiential Marketing.
2. To identify the gap between concept of experiential marketing and its implementation.
3. To suggest, suggestion and recommendation.

Data and Methodology:

This study is an observatory study based on secondary data. The data has been collected from various journal, books, publications and websites. Importance of Experiential Marketing According to Jack Morton Worldwide survey 75% of marketer in the US, the UK, Europe, China and Australia affirm they will increase spending on experiential marketing. As per the information by SEM Business Service Ltd in Indian market experiential marketing is holding 15% of total advertising which is expected to grow by another 10% in coming years. A survey revealed that the majority

of marketers believed "experiential marketing builds customer relationships for the long term". We can use experiential marketing to"

- To Build relationships
- To Raise awareness
- To Increase loyalty
- To Establish relevance
- To Encourage interaction and product trial
- To Create memories
- To Stimulate positive word of mouth
- To Change the mind of dissatisfied

Materials and Methods:

To capture all the important facets, outcomes, or implications associated with the complex domain of experiential marketing, an exploratory study based on the voices of the experiential marketing experts was considered an adequate methodological option to carry out this research. These valuable insights are more difficult to detect through a conventional quantitative research approach that would provide statistical relevance and generalize the findings (Williams and Moser 2019). Therefore, rather than focusing on statistical results, the current approach provides opportunities to investigate the experiential marketing phenomenon and to gain valuable insights into experiential marketing implementation steps. Thus, a theoretical framework could be designed even if the sample is a small one, unrepresentative for a certain population (McEachern et al. 2021).

Samples and Data Collection:

The data collection procedure of the current study consisted of an exploratory survey that captured the experts' views on the current development of experiential marketing capabilities. All experts had a leading role in planning or implementing experiential marketing strategies, being actively involved in the whole process of conceiving, planning, or execution.

Respondents were asked to discuss the implementation steps of developing an experiential marketing strategy, to list the benefits and the challenges of creating experiential marketing touchpoints, and to argue what are the most efficient KPIs, and what is the future look of this strategy. The data were gathered by using a questionnaire that was prepared with the help of Question Pro survey software.

Data Analysis:

Coding a frame of qualitative data is an essential aspect in the process of transforming the raw collected data into a communicative report (Linneberg and Korsgaard 2019). More-over, the process of coding in qualitative research enables collected data to be "assembled, categorized, and thematically sorted", resulting in an organized scheme ready for "the construction of meaning" (Williams and Moser 2019). Since the survey was based on open-ended questions, producing free-form, informant-driven text, the interpretative data analysis technique was applied to the data sets. After establishing a code for the themes in the process of open coding, the second level of coding, axial coding, was applied, after which the connections between themes are analyzed, and categorized. Subsequently, the authors applied inter-coder reliability (ICR) of all survey responses to provide "consistency and transparency of the coding process" (O'Connor and Joffe 2020) by asking an external expert to ensure a credible interpretation of data by facilitating the "identification, development, and refinement of themes" (McEachern et al. 2021) to ensure a credible interpretation of data. The results were also compared with other findings in the literature to assure the study validity by using data triangulation.

Results:

The main research problem addressed in this study is the opportunity for

companies to design and perform experiential marketing strategies to increase both customers' value and business outcomes. The results are presented for each of the research objectives in the following subsections.

Experiential Marketing Strategy: Implementation Steps, Key Performance Indicators:

Experiential marketing may include a variety of marketing activities toward immersing customers within a brand's products by attracting them in a multisensory journey. But for that to happen, marketing specialists need to undertake a range of experiential marketing implementations steps that were identified by the selected experts. These activities include concept development, promotional event management, brand activation, tech tool selection, financial management, and effective budget execution, and evaluation. As a result, all these key activities take the form of the type of events that promote a product or a service through direct contact with consumers.

These events were mentioned in the answers, the most popular being the roadshows, in-store events, exhibitions, interactive trade show booths, or ride-and-drive events. Interestingly, finding the audience's interests and emotional buttons can predict if an experiential marketing campaign is effective.

The experts stated that the success of the experience lies in the unique combination of the nature of the product, audience, market awareness, and the activities planned around the product. For launching a new product during an experiential marketing campaign it is crucial to deliver the experience on a multisensory level because it is engaging and enables customers to interact directly with a certain product or a brand. Therefore, consumers should be able to process the experiential

touchpoints through all visual, auditory, and tactile modalities.

One expert described a successful marketing experiential event as follows:

“A successful event occurred when we were able to successfully identify the target market and then learn about customers' overall needs and desires. From here, we crafted a campaign that would best touch the customers. Consumers processed the experiential touchpoints through visual—the activation was held in an environment they wanted, it was held inside of a mobile unit that was crafted to their liking, through auditory—as we had sales representatives there talking about the product—and finally, through take-home items, including samples of the product as well as prizes or give-aways”.

Challenges of Creating Experiential Marketing Touchpoints:

While there are many benefits associated with this marketing approach, there are inevitably some challenges involving experiential marketing that needs to be overcome to better scale the experiential event. To retain its competitive edge, a leading brand needs to implement the trends in customer behavior, technology, and the right engagement at the right time. Considering the challenges that the experts are facing, the key aspect targets the current COVID-19 pandemic situation that makes consumers avoid certain experiences, and together with the restrictions that do not allow organizing live events, it creates challenges for marketers to interact with their target audience. Therefore, specialists try to find innovative ways to reach consumers in their homes with the help of digital tools and virtual platforms, as a sample member pointed out: “With the pandemic, there will be a higher need for experiential marketing. First, the desire and need for experiential marketing will increase given the lack of personal interaction,

customers want to go back to experience. Second, the experiential marketing activities will evolve and focus on more exclusive and intimate activities to minimize risks. And third, especially live experiential marketing will be all about feeling safe, so we as experts will need to learn how to address an additional challenge and make it to our advantage”.

However, excluding the COVID-19 pandemic, conceiving of the “big experiential marketing idea” might be stimulating for marketers because it always has to be different and innovative, in order to provide “never-before-experience” and “cut-the-clutter” key factors. Another main challenge refers to providing a personalized experience to a large audience, a characteristic that will consume a lot of financial resources.

Given resource constraints, many event organizers choose to share costs by partnering up with other brands and sponsors. These partners can often be cheaper than a full-time hire, freeing up your budget for other uses. In a more detailed manner, two respondents concede:

“In our case, the challenges involved the planning, security, and liability of handling a big in-presence event, looking after norms and local laws regarding young, teenagers’ involvement. As well as all the logistics for events, press conferences and live presentations with the shows celebrities in both markets”.

Current Dynamics and Future Look of Experiential Marketing Strategy:

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in drastic changes to marketing, and especially to communication strategy, encouraging companies to reconsider their strategies, developing experiential marketing campaigns in order to maintain a sustainable revenue. Suddenly, consumers’ perceptions of marketing have changed, with a growing number of brands understanding the need to

use digital technology to create customer experiences.

Nowadays, brands want real emotional experiences that connect the online and offline environments, building customer loyalty and retention.

Experts envision experiential marketing strategy implemented in large venues having people constantly interacting with digital tools that will let them experience the marketing touchpoints more deeply, with the opportunity to amplify the brand’s experience and grow coverage. As follows, two experts consider that with accurate experiential marketing strategy and intelligent use of technology any brand can succeed:

“Experiential marketing is evolving more rapidly than ever before because of digital evolution and the COVID-19 pandemic. Augmented reality, virtual reality, mixed reality are the kind of technology which is yet to be explored to the fullest potential. I can be sure that technology, together with digital and experiential factors will revolutionize the marketing industry.

Suggestions and Recommendations:

The objective of the company using experiential marketing approach should always towards providing positive experience of product or service to the customer and in return gain loyalty and good will from them. The strategy of experiential marketing should be diverse and multifaceted.

Before integrating it with other methods loop points should be checked. Experiential marketing differ from product to product so the strategy should be conceptualized and implemented with definite planning to achieve goals of the company and gain competitive advantage. To get a better grasp of experiential marketing it should develop in a different way and give a positive experience in the mind of customer. The aim of the

approach should diminish the disconnection between what a company says about its offering and what customer actually encounters. The well planned and strong strategy can make a good impact on the buying pattern of customers. The strategy should have ability to do things in a competitive way. This new marketing mix is trying to bring brands to life through experience. Experiential marketing is to stimulate in active manner, to engage consumer in a personal life experience.

Conclusion:

Traditional Marketing already blessed us with valuable set of strategy, different methodology and implementation tools. Now we have entered in new era of information Technology so the approach is shifting from Traditional to Experiential Marketing. Experience provide sensory, emotional cognitive behavioral and rational value that replace functional value. Experiential Marketing is powerful instrument it consider consumer as rational and emotional human being who concerned with achieving pleasurable experiences so company need to consider new concept and approaches within the organization, Companies have to recognize the change in Marketing and its implementation to maximize the returns create and add the value of life.

Experiential marketing has proven to be an effective strategy, which uses several modes and techniques to create memorable experiences. This marketing strategy has a significant impact on consumer perception, bringing many advantages for both consumers and companies. Experts outlined the key brand benefits that include brand equity tenets, such as brand awareness, brand association, brand experience, and brand loyalty. Leveraging the power of positive brand equity, companies can sustain market share and increase customer value.

Even if many of the benefits coincide with the results of the study of author Datta (2017), changing the mind of dissatisfied customers, verifying the target audience, and establishing relevance are aspects that might help companies have the desired impact and results. The perception of consumers, their buying decisions, and their loyalty depend greatly on the direct interactions with the offerings of a brand. Therefore, as was suggested in the current study and by authors Liu et al. in their recent research as well (Liu et al. 2020), marketing specialists should design a customer journey map with a focus on maximizing the experiential customer touchpoints, ensuring value proposition engagement with the customers. Given all these considerations, the answer to the research question is that an experiential marketing strategy could offer benefits for both customers' value and business outcomes.

References:

1. Alcañiz, Mariano, Enrique Bigné, and Jaime Guixeres. 2019. Virtual Reality in Marketing: A Framework, Review, and Research Agenda. *Frontiers in Psychology* 10: 1530. [CrossRef]
2. Almubarak, Alanoud F., Simon J. Pervan, and Lester W. Johnson. 2017. A conceptual analysis of brand intimacy on social media platforms. *Journal of Strategic Marketing* 26: 463–78. [CrossRef]
3. Aronne, Lobo de Vasconcelos, ed. 2009. *The Impact of Experiential Marketing on the Customer's Perception of a Brand's Essence*. Paper presented at the XXXIII Encontro da ANPAD, São Paulo, Brazil, September 19–23.
4. Assaf, A. George, and Vincent Magnini. 2012. Accounting for customer satisfaction in measuring hotel efficiency: Evidence from the US hotel industry. *International*

- Journal of Hospitality Management 31: 642–47. [CrossRef]
5. Battarbee, Katja, and Ilpo Koskinen. 2005. Co-experience: User experience as interaction. *CoDesign* 1: 5–18. [CrossRef]
 6. Carù, Antonella, and Bernard Cova. 2008. Small versus big stories in framing consumption experiences. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal* 11: 166–76. [CrossRef]
 7. Chaney, Damien, Renaud Lunardo, and Rémi Mencarelli. 2018. Consumption experience: Past, present and future. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal* 21: 402–20. [CrossRef]
 8. Chang, Wen-Jung. 2020. Experiential marketing, brand image and brand loyalty: A case study of Starbucks. *British Food Journal* 123:209–23. [CrossRef]
 9. Cliffe, Simon J., and Judy Motion. 2005. Building contemporary brands: A sponsorship-based strategy. *Journal of Business Research* 58:1068–77. [CrossRef]
 10. Cuellar, Steven S., Robert C. Eyer, and Rich Fanti. 2015. Experiential Marketing and Long-Term Sales. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing* 32: 534–53.
 11. Datta, Veto. 2017. A conceptual study on experiential marketing: Importance, strategic issues and its impact. *International Journal of Research-GRANTHAALAYAH* 5: 26–30. [CrossRef]
 12. Felix, Egboro. 2015. Marketing Challenges of Satisfying Consumers Changing Expectations and Preferences in a Competitive Market. *International Journal of Marketing Studies* 7: 41. [CrossRef]
 13. Gentile, Chiara, Nicola Spiller, and Giuliano Noci. 2007. How to Sustain the Customer Experience. *European Management Journal* 25:395–410. [CrossRef]
 14. Ginevičius, Romualdas, and Aleksandras Vytautas Rutkauskas, eds. 2012. *The 7th International Scientific Conference “Business and Management 2012”*. Vilnius: Vilnius Gediminas Technical University Publishing House Technika.
 15. Cuellar, S. S., Eyer, R. C., & Fanti, R. (2015). Experiential Marketing and Long-Term Sales. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 32(5), 534-553.
 16. Holbrook (2000) believed that when markets enter into the period of experiential marketing, the major focuses will change from product performance to experiences entertainment
 17. Holbrook, M. B. (2000). The millennial consumer in the texts of our times: Experience and entertainment. *Journal of Macro marketing*, 20(2), 178-192.
 18. Holbrook, M. B., & Hirschman, E. C. (1982). The experiential aspects of consumption: Consumer fantasies, feelings, and fun. *Journal of consumer research*, 132-140. [5]
 19. Kotler, P. (2003). *Marketing Insights from A to Z: 80 Concepts Every Manager Needs to Know*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. [6]
 20. Lee, M. S., Hsiao, H. D., & Yang, M. F. (2011). The study of the relationship among experiential marketing, service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. *The International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 3(2), 353-379. [7]